

The signal

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We want to occupy with the propagation of signals in the special theory of relativity:

An object moves along the x-axis with the velocity v . To the time $t = 0$ the signal passes the zero point. After the time t_1 a signal is sent from the zero point. The signal moves with the velocity c . Then the signal passes the object at the time t_2 .

$$v \cdot t_2 = c \cdot (t_2 - t_1)$$

It follows:

$$t_2 = \frac{c \cdot t_1}{c - v}$$

For the time of the object itself it is valid $\Delta t' = \Delta t \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$ (time dilatation).
We obtain:

$$t'_2 = \frac{c \cdot t_1}{c - v} \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = \frac{c \cdot t_1}{c - v} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}}{c} = t_1 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{c^2 - v^2}{(c - v)^2}}$$

with $c^2 - v^2 = (c + v) \cdot (c - v)$:

$$t'_2 = t_1 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{c + v}{c - v}}$$

At the time t'_2 the signal reaches the object relative to the reference system of the object.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Particular problems of special relativity theory" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002